

KITCHEN LABORATORY: UTILIZING CHICKEN WING DISSECTION AS HOME-BASED BIOLOGY EXPERIMENT IN TEACHING MUSCULOSKELETAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Dissection has been an important part of students' experiential learning in anatomy. It helps them learn about the morphological features of animals and appreciate the complexity of organisms in a hands-on learning environment. However, the COVID-19 pandemic brought us into a situation where experiential learning is hindered because school facilities and laboratories are inaccessible for teachers and students. Considering household kitchens as an alternative science laboratory, this study utilized "Chicken wing dissection" as a home-based biology experiment in teaching and learning musculoskeletal system. The study aimed to determine the effects of chicken wing dissection on students' learning gains and attitudes towards science. The experiment was performed by 30 high school students under the supervision of their teacher and parents at home. A quasi-experimental research design was employed in this study. Parallel standardized tests, interview, and survey questionnaires on parent and students' readiness, perception, motivation, and attitudes towards biology were used as data-gathering instruments. The study revealed that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. Furthermore, all indicators of students' attitude towards science including perception to chicken wing dissection (3.96), enjoyment (3.78), anxiety level (1.92), and relevance of science in society (3.78), showed significant improvement. The study emphasized the perceptions and feedback of the parents and students on the experiment as engaging, fun, motivating, affordable, and risk-free. This means that chicken wing dissection improved students' learning outcomes and attitudes towards biology.

Keywords: Chicken Wing Dissection, Home-based Biology Experiments, Attitude Towards Biology, Philippines